

Innovation in process data technology: Roadmap for 2025–2027

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1 Inprodat focus for the period 2025–2027

1.1 Process data technology and scope of Inprodat at large

The general area of activity of the Innovation Centre for Process Data Technology (Inprodat e.V.) is defined by its statutes document. Therein, it is stated:

- “The fields of work of the association comprise process data technology and adjacent areas of computer science, engineering sciences, and applied mathematics.”
- “Process data technology here refers to the application of methods from data technology in chemical and process engineering.” The word used for chemical and process engineering in the original is *Verfahrenstechnik*.
- “This includes the analysis of economic and social implications of innovation in the mentioned fields.”

The above specifies a definition of process data technology that is binding for Inprodat and its activities, while at the same time permitting work within adjacent areas of computer science, engineering, mathematics, and social sciences.

However, what the above definition is meant to do is specify the *maximum extent of our field of work* – all the disciplines that *can* be considered. It is impossible at any given point in time to address all of this field in its complete breadth. Instead, a clear focus is needed on a few more narrow lines of work, where Inprodat members can experience a synergy when collaborating, and where we together can achieve a strong output, establishing ourselves as an academic community organization that is actually useful in practice.

1.2 Open-ended questions to guide the discussion

The following open-ended questions were formulated:

- Connecting data and information: This comprises (a) clear definitions of data structures and (b) interfaces/application programming interfaces. Do we really have clear specifications of all the data formats, data structures, APIs, *etc.*, that we are using in practice?

- What does “process” relate to? → is it “any” process? Or process in the sense of process/chemical engineering? Following our statutes, we are committed to data technology in process/chemical engineering.
- What “data” or “process data” are being considered?
- Interoperability of models and model classes – what do we mean by it?
- Does “process data technology” address academic and industrial aspects? Does it want to transfer from one to the other? Or only one of the two?
- Storing process data: Questions on where they are to be stored – *e.g.*, what hardware is used? Legal questions on who owns data, *e.g.*, in the DDB or the MolMod DB? What are future requirements (*e.g.*, ontologies, technical alignment)?
- What are likely future directions for process data *technologies*? What are requirements for future technologies in this field? What is missing/not working at the moment?

1.3 Methodology for the present analysis

We will next proceed to identify focus areas where our joint work is most likely to lead to synergies between members of the association and lead to results and publications with a high academic impact. As a basis for this, it will be evaluated what topics the members have been publishing on most successfully within the period 2021–2023, measured by the number of citations to their research articles. The eight most successful papers each year will be listed (among those that are in the top two for a person), resulting in a collection of 24 high-impact papers co-authored by the members of Inprodat in that time period.

Based on shared subfields and topics within process data technology, a subset of these papers will be grouped into six comparably narrow themes, with each theme containing at least three papers from the list. By this approach, the selected themes will be design account for at least 75% of our high-impact research. The recommendation is to focus on these six themes together within the 2025–2027 time period, addressing them through joint activities, including dedicated tracks in a workshop to be organized in 2026.

After three years (toward end of 2027), this exercise is to be repeated, based on an evaluation of Inprodat members’ publications in 2024–2026; in this way, then, a new set of themes is to be identified for the three-year period thereafter.

2 Analysis of high-impact publications

2.1 Evaluating the publication record

Top eight publications each year, from 2021 to 2023, by number of citations on Google Scholar.¹ Therein, we include up to the top two publications from each member each year, as listed on Google Scholar, to avoid too strong of an influence from any single person’s publication record. In some cases, members did not have a Google Scholar profile, or the profile was clearly incomplete; we have fixed this within reasonable effort, without any guarantee of completeness.

¹Citation status on Google Scholar captured on 31st December 2024.

Top articles published in 2021

1. “ms2: A molecular simulation tool for thermodynamic properties, release 4.0,” doi:10.1016/j.cpc.2021.107860; #1 from Gabriela Guevara, Simon Stephan, and Jadran Vrabec; 58 citations.
2. “Mass transfer through vapour-liquid interfaces: A molecular dynamics simulation study,” doi:10.1080/00268976.2020.1810798; #2 from Simon Stephan; 49 citations.
3. “Diffusion of the carbon dioxide-ethanol mixture in the extended critical region,” doi:10.1039/d0cp04985a; #2 from Gabriela Guevara and Jadran Vrabec; 27 citations.
4. “Principles of fibrinogen fiber assembly in vitro,” doi:10.1002/mabi.2020-00412; #1 from Michael Noeske; 26 citations.
5. “Semantic interoperability based on the European Materials and Modeling Ontology and its ontological paradigm: Mereosemiotics,” doi:10.23967/wccm-eccomas.2020.297; #1 from Silvia Chiacchiera, Martin Horsch, Michael Seaton, and Ilian Todorov; 25 citations.
6. *Defining Research Software: A Controversial Discussion*, doi:10.5281/zenodo.5504016; #2 from Ilian Todorov; 23 citations.
7. “OSMO: Ontology for simulation, modelling, and optimization”; #2 from Silvia Chiacchiera, Martin Horsch, and Michael Seaton; 18 citations.
8. *Adhesive Bonding of Aircraft Composite Structures*, doi:10.1007/978-3-319-92810-4; #2 from Michael Noeske; 18 citations.

Top articles published in 2022

1. *FAIR principles for research software (FAIR4RS principles)*, doi:10.15497/rda00068; #1 from Ilian Todorov; 117 citations.
2. “Transport properties of binary Lennard-Jones mixtures: Insights from entropy scaling and conformal solution theory,” doi:10.1080/00268976.2022.2057364; #1 from Simon Stephan; 27 citations.
3. “Droplet coalescence by molecular dynamics and phase-field modeling,” doi:10.1063/5.0086131; #1 from Jadran Vrabec; 26 citations.
4. “Molecular dynamics simulation study of heat transfer across solid-fluid interfaces in a simple model system,” doi:10.1080/00268976.2022.2057364; #2 from Simon Stephan; 24 citations.
5. “Experimental investigation of organic Rankine cycle performance using alkanes or hexamethyldisiloxane as a working fluid,” doi:10.1016/j.ecmx.2022.100244; #2 from Jadran Vrabec; 18 citations.
6. “Sampling the bulk viscosity of water with molecular dynamics simulation in the canonical ensemble,” doi:10.1021/acs.jpcc.2c06035; #1 from Gabriela Guevara and Peter Klein; 15 citations.

7. “Thermodynamics of supercritical carbon dioxide mixtures across the Widom line,” doi:10.1039/d2cp02701a; #1 from Gabriela Guevara; 12 citations.
8. “Interoperability and architecture requirements analysis and metadata standardization for a research data infrastructure in catalysis,” doi:10.1007/978-3-031-12285-9_10; #1 from Martin Horsch; 12 citations.

Top articles published in 2023

1. “Comparison of force fields for the prediction of thermophysical properties of long linear and branched alkanes,” doi:10.1021/acs.jpcc.2c07997; #1 from Simon Stephan; 35 citations.
2. “Molecular dynamics simulation of the Stribeck curve: Boundary lubrication, mixed lubrication, and hydrodynamic lubrication on the atomistic level,” doi:10.1007/s40544-023-0745-y; #2 from Simon Stephan; 31 citations.
3. “Mass transfer through vapor-liquid interfaces studied by non-stationary molecular dynamics simulations,” doi:10.1021/acs.jpcc.2c08752; #1 from Martin Horsch; 18 citations.
4. “Phase equilibria and interface properties of hydrocarbon propellant-oxygen mixtures in the transcritical regime,” doi:10.1063/5.0138973; #1 from Jadran Vrabec; 13 citations.
5. “Equation of state for the Mie (λ_r , 6) fluid with a repulsive exponent from 11 to 13,” doi:10.1063/5.0133412; #2 from Jadran Vrabec; 11 citations.
6. *Metadata4Ing: An Ontology for Describing the Generation of Research Data Within a Scientific Activity*, doi:10.5281/zenodo.8382665; #2 from Martin Horsch; 10 citations.
7. “Interactive molecular dynamics in virtual reality for modelling materials and catalysts,” doi:10.1016/j.jmngm.2023.108606; #1 from Ilian Todorov; 9 citations.
8. “Diffusion in liquid mixtures,” doi:10.1038/s41526-022-00246-z; #1 from Gabriela Guevara; 9 citations.

2.2 Research themes from clusters of high-impact work

Out of the 24 publications listed above, 20 can be grouped into six themes where Inprodat members have succeeded to deliver high-impact research; *i.e.*, the six themes together account for 83.3% of our high-impact research activity.

2.2.1 Research software development, publication, and maintenance

High-impact publications in topical cluster:

- N. P. Chue Hong *et al.*, *FAIR principles for research software (FAIR4RS principles)*, **2022**. Involved from Inprodat: Ilian Todorov.

- R. Fingerhut *et al.*, “ms2: A molecular simulation tool for thermodynamic properties, release 4.0,” **2021**. Involved from Inprodat: Gabriela Guevara, Simon Stephan, Jadran Vrabec.
- M. Gruenpeter *et al.*, *Defining Research Software: A Controversial Discussion*, **2021**. Involved from Inprodat: Ilian Todorov.

Four members of Inprodat contributed to the selected papers under this theme.

Developing and maintaining simulation codes is a central part of the work in process data technology; all other activities in the field depend on it. This is here connected to the questions of how to publish and cite research software, how to keep different versions of a simulation code FAIR, and thus contribute to the reproducibility of simulation results.

2.2.2 Molecular model characterization and parameterization

- S. Schmitt *et al.*, “Comparison of force fields for the prediction of thermo-physical properties of long linear and branched alkanes,” **2023**. Involved from Inprodat: Simon Stephan.
- D. Fertig *et al.*, “Transport properties of binary Lennard-Jones mixtures: Insights from entropy scaling and conformal solution theory,” **2022**. Involved from Inprodat: Simon Stephan.
- S. Pohl *et al.*, “Equation of state for the Mie (λ_r , 6) fluid with a repulsive exponent from 11 to 13,” **2023**. Involved from Inprodat: Jadran Vrabec.

Two members of Inprodat contributed to the selected papers under this theme.

There is more potential for synergy between members in this field, as there were no collaborations between them among the high-impact papers.

2.2.3 Applied ontology and knowledge representation

- M. T. Horsch *et al.*, “Semantic interoperability based on the European Materials and Modelling Ontology and its ontological paradigm: Mereosemiotics,” **2021**. Involved from Inprodat: Silvia Chiacchiera, Martin Horsch, Michael Seaton, Ilian Todorov.
- A. Karmacharya *et al.*, *Metadata4Ing: An Ontology for Describing the Generation of Research Data Within a Scientific Activity*, **2022**. Involved from Inprodat: Martin Horsch.
- M. T. Horsch *et al.*, “OSMO: Ontology for simulation, modelling, and optimization,” **2021**. Involved from Inprodat: Silvia Chiacchiera, Martin Horsch, Michael Seaton, Ilian Todorov.
- M. Horsch *et al.*, “Interoperability and architecture requirements analysis and metadata standardization for a research data infrastructure in catalysis,” **2022**. Involved from Inprodat: Martin Horsch.

Four members of Inprodat contributed to high-impact publications in this field.

2.2.4 Molecular simulation of fluid transport properties

High-impact publications in topical cluster:

- R. Chatwell *et al.*, “Diffusion of the carbon dioxide–ethanol mixture in the extended critical region,” **2021**. Involved from Inprodat: Gabriela Guevara, Jadran Vrabec.
- R. Hafner *et al.*, “Sampling the bulk viscosity of water with molecular dynamics simulation in the canonical ensemble,” **2022**. Involved from Inprodat: Gabriela Guevara, Peter Klein, Jadran Vrabec.
- A. Vailati *et al.*, “Diffusion in liquid mixtures,” **2023**. Involved from Inprodat: Gabriela Guevara.

Three members of Inprodat contributed to the selected papers under this theme.

This refers to transport properties of the homogeneous bulk fluid (for transport at interfaces and in multiphase systems, it is contained in theme no. 5).

2.2.5 Molecular modelling of phenomena at fluid interfaces

High-impact publications in topical cluster:

- S. Stephan *et al.*, “Mass transfer through vapour-liquid interfaces: A molecular dynamics simulation study,” **2021**. Involved from Inprodat: Simon Stephan.
- M. Heinen *et al.*, “Droplet coalescence by molecular dynamics and phase-field modeling,” **2022**. Involved from Inprodat: Jadran Vrabec.
- D. Schaefer *et al.*, “Mass transfer through vapor-liquid interfaces studied by non-stationary molecular dynamics simulations,” **2023**. Involved from Inprodat: Martin Horsch, Simon Stephan.
- I. Nitzke *et al.*, “Phase equilibria and interface properties of hydrocarbon propellant-oxygen mixtures in the transcritical regime,” **2023**. Involved from Inprodat: Simon Stephan, Jadran Vrabec.

Three members of Inprodat contributed to the selected papers under this theme.

Work on equilibrium properties increasingly combines MD simulation with gradient models such as one-dimensional density gradient theory and three-dimensional phase field modelling. Molecular equations of state are used to connect the molecular to the continuum level. Another focus has been on interfacial transport properties and interfacial dynamics from MD simulation.

2.2.6 Solid surfaces, adsorption, adhesion, lubrication, and coatings

- S. Stephan *et al.*, “Molecular dynamics simulation of the Stribeck curve: Boundary lubrication, mixed lubrication, and hydrodynamic lubrication on the atomistic level,” **2023**. Involved from Inprodat: Simon Stephan.
- S. Schmitt *et al.*, “Molecular dynamics simulation study of heat transfer across solid-fluid interfaces in a simple model system,” **2022**. Involved from Inprodat: Simon Stephan.

- W. L. Cavalcanti *et al.* (eds.), *Adhesive Bonding of Aircraft Composite Structures*, 2021. Involved from Inprodat: Michael Noeske.

Two members of Inprodat contributed to high-impact publications in this field.

There could be a potential for collaborative work and synergy between the colleagues listed above (Michael Noeske, Simon Stephan) and the Inprodat members involved in VIPCOAT (Peter Klein, Natalia Konchakova, Heinz Preisig).

2.3 Criteria for being on topic for Inprodat in 2025–2027

Above, we have identified six clusters of work that, by construction, covers $\geq 75\%$ of the publications with a high academic impact published by our members in recent years. However, not all of this work is within process data technology; for this, it needs to combine a data, semantics, modelling, or simulation orientation on the one hand with a process, chemical, or mechanical engineering orientation on the other hand. In addition, work will be positioned stronger within the focus of Inprodat if it connects multiple of the clusters identified as our strengths.

Accordingly, the following is recommended as the scope for the six topical tracks within Inprodat; this mainly concerns our planned workshop (2026). So specially concerning contributions to the 2026 workshop, the following will be considered on topic:

1. *Research software development, publication, and maintenance.* Work with a *primary focus* in “research software development, publication, and maintenance” (theme 1) is on topic within track 1 if it has a *secondary focus* in any of the other themes. In particular, work on research software for molecular modelling or applied ontology is always on topic.
2. *Molecular model characterization and parameterization.* Work with a *primary focus* in “molecular model characterization and parameterization” (theme 2) is in general on scope within track 2; no further conditions.
3. *Applied ontology and knowledge representation.* Work with a *primary focus* in “applied ontology and knowledge representation” is on topic within track 3 whenever it has a use case or application scenario related to research data infrastructures in engineering, chemical and engineering data, or in research software and model development and publication in engineering.
4. *Molecular simulation of fluid transport properties.* Work with a *primary focus* in “molecular simulation of fluid transport properties” (theme 4) is in general on scope within track 4; no further conditions.
5. *Molecular modelling of phenomena at fluid interfaces.* Work with a *primary focus* in “molecular modelling of phenomena at fluid interfaces” (theme 5) is in general on scope within track 5; no further conditions.
6. *Solid surfaces, adsorption, adhesion, lubrication, and coatings.* Work with a *primary focus* in *solid surfaces, adsorption, adhesion, lubrication, and coatings* (theme 6) is on topic within track 6 if it has a *secondary focus* in any of the other themes.

3 Roadmap implementation timeline

21st February 2025:

- Bids for hosting the Inprodat 2026 Workshop presented; first discussion.
- Draft 2025–2027 roadmap presented and discussed; decision on desired modifications, extensions, revisions, and redactions.
- Final agreement on the six scientific tracks mentioned in the roadmap, which will also be used as the six tracks of the workshop programme.

16th May 2025:

- Approval and publication of the finalized roadmap for 2025–2027.
- Possibility to present supplementary bids for hosting the 2026 workshop.
- Final decision on hosting and basic framework for the 2026 workshop.

8th August 2025:

- Regular Inprodat call.

Some point between 29th September and 8th October 2025: Annual General Meeting, in person, Kaiserslautern:

- Final approval of the scientific committee and the call for papers (with extended abstract submission due in February) for the Inprodat 2026 Workshop. The scientific committee will contain of the order of four persons, chaired by the workshop’s main organizer, who are all nominated by us.
- Election of the new board, to remain in office for the coming three years, consisting of four members (down from eight), each with a key role:
 1. Following Inprodat statutes § 6 (1) no. 1, the chair of the association; this person should invite to regular board meetings open to all members (as of now, once every 12 weeks), take care of the agenda and the minutes, and represent Inprodat for most purposes to others.
 2. Following Inprodat statutes § 6 (1) no. 2, the vice chair; this should be the person in charge of organizing the upcoming Inprodat workshop (and chair of its scientific committee), as it will be helpful for the organizer to be on the executive board.
 3. Following Inprodat statutes § 6 (1) no. 3, the treasurer; it should be somebody based in Germany to simplify interactions with the bank. The treasurer is also the LEAR and takes part in bid management.
 4. Following Inprodat statutes § 6 (1) no. 4, one additional member of the extended board (down from five additional members). This role should be taken by a person who will work on organizing a journal special issue related to the workshop.

Reducing the number of board members will make the board size more proportionate to the number of members of the association and also free up resources for committee work other than that of the board.

- Elect a new revisions committee, consisting of two members (as it does now), and a new gender equality committee, consisting of two members (down from three), each for a term of three years. These committees have not properly functioned so far, but their work will be needed in the future. The members of the revisions committee should be German-speaking, since some of the relevant documents could be in German.

Day after the AGM:

- In-person notary appointment of the members of the new executive board.
- In-person bank appointment of the members of the new executive board.

31st October 2025:

- First joint zoom meeting of the new executive board and extended board, open to all members. Scheduling the future Inprodat zoom calls.
- Confirm that the workshop website and the submission portal are functional. (This is the responsibility of the workshop organizers.)
- Required material with notary confirmation has been communicated to the register court; the postal contact address for the association, which is still set to Peter's home address, will be set to an appropriate contact address (private or business, whichever makes sense) of the new treasurer.
- Additionally (same appointment, right after the board meeting), first meeting of the gender equality committee and the revisions committee, where they determine their delegates to the bid management committee.

Mid December 2025:

- Abstract deadline for the Inprodat 2026 Workshop.

First quarter of 2026:

- January: Notifications sent to contributors to the workshop. Organizational bank account must be functional (responsibility of the treasurer). Gender equality plan for 2026, based on the associations's activities in 2025 (responsibility of gender equality committee). Plans for the special issue related to the workshop discussed and approved.
- February/March: 2026 Workshop held as an in-person event. Book of abstracts released as a simple PDF document with a DOI. Confirm with participants whether they will write a paper for the planned special issue.

Remainder of 2026:

- Annual general meeting held. No elections at this meeting.
- We figure out whether there are enough submissions to go ahead with the special issue.
- If yes: Special issue manuscripts submitted and reviewed.

Year 2027:

- Approve and release the gender equality plan for 2027, based on the association's activities in 2026 (responsibility of the gender equality committee).
- Publication of the journal special issue on the 2026 workshop.
- In advance of the annual general meeting, repeat the process of renewing the member list (same as done in 2024 before the annual general meeting): Existing members are invited to give a signal, in whichever way they prefer, that they want to continue to be members of Inprodat. Upon doing so, they are taken over to the new member list. There is no deadline for this.
- Annual general meeting held. (No elections at this meeting.)
- Draft 2028–2030 roadmap presented and discussed; decision on desired modifications, extensions, revisions, and redactions.